

РОССИЙСКАЯ АКАДЕМИЯ НАУК
Южный научный центр

RUSSIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES
Southern Scientific Centre

Кавказский Энтомологический Бюллетень

CAUCASIAN ENTOMOLOGICAL BULLETIN

Том 16. Вып. 2

Vol. 16. No. 2

Ростов-на-Дону
2020

Notes on a synonymy in the tribe Platyscelidini (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae)

© M.V. Nabozhenko^{1, 2}, L.V. Egorov³

¹Precaspian Institute of Biological Resources of the Dagestan Federal Research Centre of the Russian Academy of Sciences, M. Gadzhiev str., 45, Makhachkala, Republic of Dagestan 367000 Russia. E-mail: nalassus@mail.ru

²Dagestan State University, M. Gadzhiev str., 43a, Makhachkala, Republic of Dagestan 367000 Russia

³Prisursky State Nature Reserve, Lesnoy Settl., 9, Cheboksary 428034 Russia. E-mail: platyscelis@mail.ru

Abstract. Reitter described two genus-rank taxa within the tenebrionid tribe Helopini (Tenebrionidae) in the same work: *Euryhelops* Reitter, 1902 (type species *Helops tiro* Reitter, 1902) as a subgenus of the genus *Helops* Fabricius, 1775 and *Euryhelops* Reitter, 1902 as a separate genus (type species *Helops championi* Reitter, 1891 = *Helops subaeneus* Reitter, 1889). He eliminated this homonymy in the same 1902 but in a different paper and proposed the generic name *Zophohelops* Reitter, 1902 (Helopini) for the first taxon. The second taxon *Euryhelops* was erroneously placed as a junior synonym to the subgenus *Cardiobioramix* Kaszab, 1940 (type species *Bioramix asidioides* Bates, 1879) in the genus *Bioramix* Bates, 1879 (Platyscelidini). Both type species of *Euryhelops* and *Cardiobioramix* are consubgeneric, therefore we reinstate the priority of the name *Euryhelops* as a subgenus within the genus *Bioramix* and propose the following synonymy: *Euryhelops* Reitter, 1902, **subgen. resurr.** = *Cardiobioramix* Kaszab, 1940, **syn. n.**

Key words: darkling beetles, Helopini, Platyscelidini, synonymy, nomenclature.

Замечания по синонимии в трибе Platyscelidini (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae)

© М.В. Набоженко^{1, 2}, Л.В. Егоров³

¹Прикаспийский институт биологических ресурсов – обособленное подразделение Федерального государственного бюджетного учреждения науки Дагестанского федерального исследовательского центра Российской академии наук, ул. М. Гаджиева, 45, Махачкала, Республика Дагестан 367000 Россия. E-mail: nalassus@mail.ru

²Дагестанский государственный университет, ул. М. Гаджиева, 43а, Махачкала, Республика Дагестан 367000 Россия

³Государственный природный заповедник «Присурский», пос. Лесной, 9, Чебоксары 428034 Россия. E-mail: platyscelis@mail.ru

Резюме. Рейттер описал в составе трибы Helopini (Tenebrionidae) два надвидовых таксона в одной работе: *Euryhelops* Reitter, 1902 (типовой вид *Helops tiro* Reitter, 1902) как подрод рода *Helops* Fabricius, 1775 и *Euryhelops* Reitter, 1902 как самостоятельный род (типовой вид *Helops championi* Reitter, 1891 = *Helops subaeneus* Reitter, 1889). Для устранения омонимии Рейттер в этом же году, но в другой работе предложил название *Zophohelops* Reitter, 1902 (Helopini) с родовым рангом для первого таксона. Второй таксон был ошибочно синонимизирован с подродом *Cardiobioramix* Kaszab, 1940 (типовой вид *Bioramix asidioides* Bates, 1879) в составе рода *Bioramix* Bates, 1879 (Platyscelidini). Типовые виды *Euryhelops* и *Cardiobioramix* относятся к одному подроду, поэтому мы восстанавливаем приоритет для названия Рейттера и устанавливаем следующую синонимию: *Euryhelops* Reitter, 1902, **subgen. resurr.** = *Cardiobioramix* Kaszab, 1940, **syn. n.**

Ключевые слова: жуки-чернотелки, Helopini, Platyscelidini, синонимия, номенклатура.

Reitter [1902a] used the same name for two taxa of genus level in the tribe Helopini:

1. The monotypic genus *Euryhelops* Reitter, 1902a: 209. Type species: *Helops championi* Reitter, 1891 = *Helops subaeneus* Reitter, 1889 (homonym name).

2. The subgenus *Euryhelops* Reitter, 1902a: 214, in the genus *Helops* Fabricius, 1775. Type species *Helops tiro* Reitter, 1902 by subsequent designation [Medvedev, 1987].

A little later, Reitter [1902b] increased the rank of the second taxon to a genus and eliminated this homonymy, proposing the new name *Zophohelops* Reitter, 1902 for it (type species *Helops tiro* Reitter, 1902).

Reitter didn't mentioned the first taxon (with the type species *H. championi*) further, even in his revision of the tribe Helopini [Reitter, 1922]. However later *Euryhelops* was transferred to the tribe Platyscelidini and erroneously listed as a junior synonym of the subgenus *Cardiobioramix* Kaszab, 1940 (type species *Bioramix asidioides* Bates, 1879) in the genus *Platynoscelsis* Kraatz, 1882 [Kaszab,

1940]. Kaszab [1940] also included in the subgenus *Cardiobioramix* the type species of *Euryhelops*, for which he erroneously used the preoccupied name *Platynoscelsis* (*Cardiobioramix*) *subaenea* (Reitter, 1889), although Reitter [1891] eliminated this homonymy by proposing the replacement name *Helops championi* Reitter, 1891 for *Helops subaeneus* Reitter, 1889 (nom. praeocc., non *Helops subaeneus* Baudi, 1876).

Egorov [2004] proposed the new combination *Bioramix* (*Cardiobioramix*) *championi* (Reitter, 1891) and interpreted *Euryhelops* as a junior synonym of the genus *Bioramix* Bates, 1879, as well as in subsequent publications [Egorov, 2008, 2020].

Both type species of taxa *Euryhelops* and *Cardiobioramix* belong to one subgenus [Egorov, 2004], but the first name has a priority. We cannot conserve the name *Cardiobioramix* with prevailing usage, because it does not meet two conditions of the Article 23.9 of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature [1999]. As a result, we

reinstate the independence of the name *Euryhelops* as a subgenus within the genus *Bioramix* and propose the following synonymy: *Euryhelops* Reitter, 1902, **subgen. resurr.** = *Cardiobioramix* Kaszab, 1940, **syn. n.**

Acknowledgements

The study was supported for the first author by the basic research project of the Precaspian Institute of Biological Resources of the Daghestan Federal Research Centre of the Russian Academy of Sciences, registration number AAAA-A17-117081640018-5.

References

- Egorov L.V. 2004. The classification of tenebrionid beetles of the tribe Platyscelidini (Coleoptera, Tenebrionidae) of the world fauna. *Entomological Review*. 84(6): 641–666.
- Egorov L.V. 2008. Tribe Platyscelidini Lacordaire, 1859. In: Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera. Volume 5. Tenebrionoidea. (I. Löbl, A. Smetana eds). Stenstrup: Apollo Books: 291–297.
- Egorov L.V. 2020. Tribe Platyscelidini Lacordaire, 1859. In: Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera. Volume 5. Tenebrionoidea. (D. Iwan, I. Löbl eds.). Leiden: Brill: 375–384. DOI: 10.1163/9789004434998_004
- International Commission on Zoological Nomenclature. 1999. International Code of Zoological Nomenclature. Fourth edition. London: International Trust for Zoological Nomenclature. xxix + 306 p.
- Kaszab Z. 1940. Revision der Tenebrioniden-Tribus Platyscelini (Col. Teneb.). *Mitteilungen der Münchener Entomologischen Gesellschaft*. 30(1): 119–235.
- Medvedev G.S. 1987. Darkling beetles of the genus *Zophohelops* Rtt. and close genera (Coleoptera, Tenebrionidae) of the Middle Asia and Kazakhstan. In: Trudy Zoologicheskogo instituta Akademii nauk SSSR. T. 164. Sistematika i geograficheskoe rasprostranenie zhestkokrylykh [Proceedings of the Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR. Vol. 164. Systematics and geographical distribution of Coleoptera]. Leningrad: Zoological Institute of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR: 95–129.
- Reitter E. 1891. Coleopterologische Notizen. XLI. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*. 10: 226–228.
- Reitter E. 1902a. Verschiedenes über die Coleopteren der Tenebrioniden-Abtheilung Helopina. *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift*. 1901: 209–224.
- Reitter E. 1902b. Coleopterologische Notizen. *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*. 21(10): 221–222.
- Reitter E. 1922. Bestimmungstabelle der palaearktischen Helopinae (Col. Tenebrionidae). *Wiener Entomologische Zeitung*. 39(1–4): 1–44, 113–171.

Received / Поступила: 25.10.2020

Accepted / Принята: 30.10.2020

Published online / Опубликована онлайн: 2.11.2020